

Study of a Torque Limiter Based on NiTi Pseudoelastic Tapes

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Herein, a new torsional device based on shape memory alloy elements and operating as torque limiter is presented. It consists of a set of pseudoelastic NiTi tapes working in series configuration. The tapes are assembled radially with respect to the rotational direction and work sequentially in beam-like bending mode. The trend of the resulting torque may span from pulsating to continuous by changing the number of tapes. Furthermore, the use of NiTi material enables a temperature-dependent response. Due to the particular mounting, the flag-shaped pseudoelastic mechanical behavior typical of NiTi is partially hidden; however, the use of pseudoelastic elements provides a stable cyclic response and enables the possibility to tune the output torque.

deformability for martensite. The transition between austenite and martensite can be either thermally (shape memory effect) or stress (pseudoelasticity) induced^[11] and often involves a high shape (strain) recovery. The shape memory effect consists of a macroscopic shape change between the two phases; it implicates the recovery of a pre-determined austenite shape through heating a deformed martensite. This property is reversible which means that under load austenite easily transforms into the deformed martensite through cooling. This effect is normally used to promote mechanical work, finding several interesting applications in the actuation field.^[12–15]

In addition, pseudoelasticity consists of a complete recovery of deformation through a hysteretic mechanical response. This occurs in austenitic and isothermal conditions and it follows the so-called pseudoelastic flag-shaped path: during loading, austenite first goes into an elastic deformation and then it transforms into martensite at constant stress (stress-induced martensite, SIM). As SIM is thermodynamically unstable in the austenite domain, the material freely recovers the original austenite state once the load is removed, following a path at constant stress lower than that of loading.^[9] Through the pseudoelastic mechanical cycle the material is therefore able to dissipate a large amount of energy that can be used in dampers or in mechanical systems to preserve assemblies and sensitive equipment from environmental noise and structural vibrations.^[16]

Pseudoelasticity does not require external activation energies; it is repeatable and enables the fabrication of complex, light, and safe systems with a quite simple design. Several pseudoelastic devices can be found in literature. The great part of them concerns the civil field where pseudoelasticity is used to damp the structural vibrations during a seismic event.^[17–19]

Torque limiters are widely used devices that are used as safety equipment as they are able to reduce the torque to a threshold value. They are used in many engineering applications, such as aeronautical,^[20] robotics,^[21–23] and biomechanics.^[24] They work under different operating principles among which the most used are the magnetic and the mechanical friction.

In the present study, a novel torque limiter based on pseudoelastic NiTi tapes is designed, fabricated, and tested. In particular, a meticulous study of the mechanical behavior of the presented device is addressed through the study of three different releases. The work aims to propose alternative solutions to current torque limiters as well as highlight the high potential of SMAs in the design of novel compact devices.

1. Introduction

NiTi is the most known shape memory alloy (SMA) and it is exploited in numerous industrial applications, thanks to its unique mechanical properties such as the shape memory effect and pseudoelasticity. In addition, NiTi presents high damping and fatigue properties, high strength resistance, biocompatibility and corrosion resistance. The main uses of NiTi are medicine (such as stents, grafts, orthopedic staples, orthodontic archwires, eyeglass frames), aerospace and military (such as couplers in F14 planes), safety (like dampers of seismic vibrations and sprinklers), and robotics (such as actuators).^[1–10]

At the base of the mechanical attitudes of NiTi there is a first-order thermoelastic transformation between two solid phases, austenite and martensite, that are, respectively, thermodynamically stable at high and low temperatures. Austenite and martensite differ for the crystalline lattice: highly symmetric body-centered cubic cell for austenite and monoclinic cell for martensite. The specific crystalline enables high rigidity for austenite and high

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2. Results and Discussions

2.1. The 2D CAD Model of the Torque Limiter

The study focuses on a torque limiter based on NiTi tapes and composed of a stainless steel case equipped with a shaped rotating shaft and a flanged bearing to reduce friction during rotation. Three devices were fabricated and studied, 8-T, 16-T, and 32-T, composed, respectively, of 8, 16, and 32 NiTi tapes. The 8-T device was partially presented in a previous work.^[25]

The NiTi tapes are assembled radially with respect to the rotational direction to promote a sequential beam-like bending functioning, namely, a series working configuration. No screws are used to fix the tapes to the case as a thigh circular housing was designed to keep firmly the tapes during loading. **Figure 1** shows the 2D CADs and renderings of the proposed torsional devices. **Figure 2** shows the 2D CAD of the shaft and the flanged bearing.

2.2. The NiTi Tape

Figure 3 shows the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) graphs and the mechanical response at room temperature of the NiTi tape after the thermal treatment at 500 °C. In the DSC graph, the phase transformation temperatures (start, s, peak, p, finish, f) of martensite, austenite, and rhombohedral phases are indicated with capital letters (A, M, and R, respectively); the values of the phase transition temperatures are shown in **Table 1**. DSC analysis shows that at room temperature the material is in the austenite state. The mechanical response at room temperature, as shown in **Figure 3b**, highlights a complete recovery of deformation under 5% strain.

2.3. Characterization of the 8-T Torque Limiter

Figure 4 shows the 8-T torsional damper and the detail of the circular aperture used to keep the NiTi tapes. During rotation,

Figure 2. 2D CAD of the a) stainless steel shaft and b) bearing.

the shaft imparts sequential bending action to the NiTi tapes. **Figure 5a,b**, respectively, shows the output torque of one NiTi tape upon 45° rotation and the torque of the 8-T damper upon two turns of rotation. During functioning, each tape is loaded over 45° rotation and it is at the maximum deflection at 45°; thereafter, it rapidly recovers the unbent state. However, the output torque referred to a single tape has a peak-like trend (see **Figure 5a**). The torque basically presents a peak at about 20°; subsequently, it decreases (even if the tape is still loaded) and becomes zero at 45° rotation (where the tape is at its maximum deflection). In addition, two meaningful changes of slopes are observable: the one closer to 10° is ascribed to the transition into the SIM, whereas the other at about 40° is due to the simultaneously solicitation of the next adjacent tape. This response is repeated for every tape; therefore, we register eight peaks in one full turn.

The temperature of the tapes changes according the mechanical output. This is evident from the temperature measurement accomplished on the 8-T device. **Figure 6** shows the temperature of three consecutive tapes superimposed to the output torque registered during rotation. Let us consider one single tape, as,

Figure 1. 2D images and 3D renderings of a) 8-T, b) 16-T, and c) 32-T devices.

Figure 3. a) DSC and b) beam-like bending test of the NiTi tape thermally treated at 500 °C.

Table 1. Phase transformation temperatures of the NiTi tapes after the 500 °C heat treatment.

Cooling						Heating					
R _s [°C]	R _p [°C]	R _f [°C]	M _s [°C]	M _p [°C]	M _f [°C]	R _s [°C]	R _p [°C]	A _p [°C]	A _f [°C]		
25	21.5	17	-36.5	-45	-59	9	16	23.5	26.5		

Figure 4. a) Photograph of the 8-T torsional damper and b) magnification of the thin housing designed to keep the tape.

for example, Tape 2 (red line). The transition into SIM enables the release of heat which is measurable through a change of temperature; it was observed that temperature increases from point A to point B. It means that Tape 2 is loaded between A and B and its contribution on the output torque falls in the A'-B' region of the torque measurement; this corroborates previous statements about the sequentially solicitation of consecutive tapes, also confirming that each tape starts bending when the previous tape is at its maximum deflection.

The most important outcome is that the NiTi flag-shaped pseudoelastic response is hidden. To understand this peculiar response, let us see the detail of the mechanical response of a single tape. **Figure 7** shows computer aided design (CAD) representation at 0°, 20°, and 45° rotation and 5°-step photographs of

Figure 5. a) Torque versus angle of rotation of the 8-T device registered during 45° of rotation. Arrow at 10° indicates the transition into the SIM, and the arrow at 40° indicates the angle at which two consecutive tapes are simultaneously solicited. b) Torque of the 8-T damper over two turns.

the 8-T damper over 45° rotation. The photographs demonstrate that during 45° of rotation the tape is in loading stage. Despite this, we observed a peak-like trend of the output torque (see **Figure 5a**). Three main concurrent reasons are at the base of this

Figure 6. Temperature of three consecutive tapes of the 8-T device during functioning.

Figure 8. Torque of 8-T damper over 90° of rotation at different rotation speeds.

mechanical attitude. First, the reaction force of the tape on the shaft increases with the increasing of the angle of rotation in the way reported by the mechanical curve of Figure 3. Furthermore, the point of application and the line of action of the reaction force of the tape both vary with the angle of rotation (Figure 7a). Finally, the lever arm of the component of the reaction force of the tape that provides torque is not constant during the rotation (Figure 7a).

Mechanical tests also pointed out that the 8-T damper maintains unaltered response when the rotational speed is changed. As an example, **Figure 8** shows the torque of the 8-T damper during 90° of rotation at six selected rotational speeds. Minimum variations are observed; thus, it can be stated that there is not a dependency between the torque and the rotation speed.

It is known that NiTi carries out higher loads with the increase in test temperature (Clausius–Clapeyron relationship). This

Figure 7. a) CAD representation at 0°, 20°, and 45° rotation and b) 5°-step photographs of the 8-T damper over 45° rotation.

Figure 9. a) Torque of 8-T damper as a function of the rotational speed during 90° rotation at different test temperatures. b) Maximum torque of two tapes as a function of the environmental temperature.

Figure 10. Photograph of the a) 16-T device and respective mechanical response upon b) 50° rotation and c) over two turns.

property was observed in the presented devices. In the graphs of **Figure 9**, the torque of the 8-T device over 90° rotation (i.e., two tapes' response) at four environmental temperatures and the device mean maximum torque as a function of the test temperatures are reported. It was found that the output torque increases with a rate of $0.7 \text{ Nmm } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$.

2.4. 16-T and 32-T Releases

The mechanical output of the device can be tuned and improved by the addition of further tapes. **Figure 10** shows the torsional damper composed of 16 NiTi tapes (16-T), the respective torque upon 50° rotation and over two turns. A quite relevant response was found. It can be seen that the torque never gets null, thanks to the lower distance between the tapes (the angle between two consecutive tapes is reduced to 22.5°, see **Figure 1**). The closer configuration enables an output torque that never goes to zero as there are always two or three loaded tapes during rotation, depending on the angle. As a first consequence, the torque is higher than that registered for the 8-T device. This behavior is supported by the mechanical response registered in the 0°–50° rotation range shown in **Figure 10b** and by the 5° sketches and photographs in **Figure 11**. Each tape is bent within

45° rotation as observed for the 8-T damper; however, at 15°, the bent tape hints and starts to solicit the next adjacent tape. Subsequently, at 40°, three tapes are simultaneously bent, two directly by the shaft and a third by the adjacent tape. After 45° rotation, the torque returns to be the sum of the contributions of two tapes. Henceforth, considering consecutive turns, a kind of endless plateau is promoted. This phenomenon is more evident by increasing the number of tapes. With, for example, increasing the number of tapes to 32, the device reaches higher torque with an endless plateau approximately at 0.1 Nm (**Figure 12**).

Figure 13 shows an example of the mechanical output of the three presented devices upon an eight-step sequence of clockwise and anticlockwise rotations: +360°; 0°; –180°; 0°; –90°; 0°; –45°; 0°.

A final comment should be made on the expected fatigue life of the proposed torque limiter. Through simple geometrical considerations, it can be estimated that each tape achieves an expected maximum strain of 11.5% during rotation. This working condition is detrimental for a long fatigue life of a NiTi-based device. For this reason, the geometry should be reconsidered in case the proposed torque limiter is used in an application where a high number of working cycles is mandatory, such as by considering shorter NiTi tapes.

Figure 11. a) 5°-step sketch and b) photographs of the 16-T device over 45° rotation.

Figure 12. Damper composed of 32 tapes (32-T) and respective mechanical response over 25 turns.

3. Conclusion

The work presents a compact, lightweight, and safe torsional device based on NiTi pseudoelastic tapes. The specific design along with the use of NiTi material enables several attractive

features. The most important are as follows. 1) The output torque presents a peculiar bidirectional trend which can be tuned from pulsating to continuous by increasing the number of NiTi tapes. 2) The output torque can be enhanced by increasing either the number of the NiTi tapes or the environmental temperature.

Figure 13. Torque over a sequence of clockwise and anticlockwise rotations of the a) 8-T, b) 16-T, and c) 32-T torque limiters.

Table 2. Selective laser melting’s main process parameters for SS316L.

Layer thickness [μm]	50
Laser power [W]	195
Exposure time [μs]	80
Point distance [μm]	60
Estimated scanning speed [mm s^{-1}]	750
Laser energy density [J mm^{-3}]	47.3

Figure 14. Detail of the mechanical testing setup with K-thermocouples placed on the NiTi tapes.

3) The mechanical response does not change with rotational speed and it is stable, thanks to the complete strain recovery of the NiTi tapes. 4) The mechanical stability enables a kind of endless pseudoplateau. 5) The device is environmental friendly as it does not require an external energy input.

Thanks to the particular mechanical response of NiTi, the presented torque limiter can work also as damper of free rotation. Furthermore, the mechanical output can be improved by considering different geometries of the NiTi tape (such as lower length or higher thickness). Finally, the proposed device can be easily scaled down to smaller dimension to improve the fatigue life.

4. Experimental Section

The pseudoelastic elements were cut from a commercial NiTi tape (3.6 mm width, 0.21 mm thickness, SAES Getters spa, Italy). The as-received NiTi tape was in the cold-worked state and the composition was near equiatomic with Ni \approx 51 at%. Each NiTi element followed heat treatment at 500 °C for 30 min (water quench). The phase transformation temperatures of the thermal-treated tapes were assessed by differential scanning calorimetry (Q100 TA Instr.). Measurements were accomplished at a heating/cooling rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in the range from -100 to 80 °C. Bending tests on the NiTi tape were conducted by means of a mechanical analyzer (Q800 TA Instr.) in a simple cantilever beam mode. Tests were accomplished at room temperature and in force control at 0.5 N min⁻¹.

The shaft and the case of the torsional dampers were manufactured through additive technology by a selective laser melting machine (Renishaw AM400), starting from a micrometric SS316L powder; process parameters are shown in **Table 2**.

Figure 15. Sketch of the input and output data of the mechanical tests.

Mechanical tests on the torque limiters were conducted through an Instron E3000 testing machine in torsional mode. Devices were first tested at room temperature under different rotational speeds (1, 10, 50, 100, 200, and 300° s⁻¹). In these tests, both the two main rotational directions were verified. During testing, the change of temperature of the tape ascribed to the phase transition was measured through a K-thermocouple located near the most solicited region of the tape; temperature was measured on three consecutive tapes (Figure 14). A fourth thermocouple was used to monitor the environmental temperature in the proximity of the device.

Furthermore, the effect of environmental temperature on the functional performance of the device was assessed by testing at 30, 35, 40, and 45 °C.

Finally, the devices were tested under a predefined sequence (rotation path) of clockwise and anticlockwise rotations (+360°; 0°; -180°; 0°; -90°; 0°; -45°; 0°) at 300° s⁻¹.

Figure 15 shows a sketch summarizing the input and output data of the mechanical tests considered in this work.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

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